

THE APPLICATION PROCESS OF INTERNATIONAL LAW IN SOLUTION OF TERRITORIAL CONFLICT OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA AND GEORGIA

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PROCESUL DE APLICARE A DREPTULUI INTERNAȚIONAL ÎN SOLUȚIONAREA CONFLICTULUI TERITORIAL DIN REPUBLICA MOLDOVA ȘI GEORGIA

Articolul reflectă procesul de aplicare a legislației internaționale în soluționarea conflictelor teritoriale din Republica Moldova și Georgia. Regimul dreptului internațional umanitar oferă un anumit nivel de protecție a populației, urmărirea penală a presupușilor infractori pentru crime de război, precum viol, crimă și tortură, protejarea bunurilor civile. Cu toate acestea nivelul potențial de protecție depinde de clasificarea conflictului. Articolul analizează subiectul referitor la competența aplicabilă membrilor forțelor armate ale Federației Ruse alocate pe teritoriul Republicii Moldova ca una actuală pentru dreptul internațional public. Referitor la Georgia, această țară a apelat la principiul integrității teritoriale, în timp ce Osetia de Sud a apelat la dreptul poporului la autodeterminare. În urma intervenției armate asupra Osetiei de Sud, Georgia a încălcat principiile dreptului internațional și anume: interzicerea folosirii forței sau amenințarea de forță, respectarea drepturilor omului și a libertăților fundamentale, autodeterminarea popoarelor.

Cuvinte-cheie: conflict teritorial, drept internațional, Republica Moldova, Georgia, jurisdicție extrateritorială, conflict armat, conflict înghețat.

The article reflects the application process of international law in solution of territorial conflicts of the Republic of Moldova and Georgia. The regime of international humanitarian law offers a certain level of protection for population, prosecuting alleged offenders for war crimes, such as rape, murder and torture, protecting civilian assets. However, the potential level of protection depends on the classification of the conflict. There is analyzed the subject regarding applicable jurisdiction to members of the Russian Federation's armed forces allocated on the territory of the Republic of Moldova as a current one for public international law. What about the Georgia, this country appealed to the principle of territorial integrity, while South Ossetia appealed to peoples' right to self-determination. As a result of the armed attack on South Ossetia, Georgia violated the principles of international law, namely: prohibition of the use of force or threat of force, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, as self-determination of the people.

Keywords: territorial conflict, international law, Republic of Moldova, Georgia, extraterritorial jurisdiction, armed conflict, frozen conflict.

Particularities of application the norms of international law in the context of the territorial conflict in Transnistria

The question regarding applicable jurisdiction to members of the Russian Federation armed forces allocated on the territory of the Republic of Moldova

is a current one for public international law. Considering that the principle of sovereign equality of States is one of the fundamental principles of public international law, each State retains its right to exercise jurisdiction over persons and assets located within or outside the territory of the country [1, p.39].

Under these circumstances, a single solution cannot exist, such situations being governed by international agreements, including bilateral and multilateral agreements. International agreements might provide for the application of the jurisdiction of the State under certain conditions, the requirements for the surrender and extradition of persons, the establishment of Inquiry or Conciliation Commissions for the purpose of settling conflicts.

One of the criteria characterizing the state as a subject of international law is the exercise of jurisdiction in relation to assets and persons. It is obvious that in the absence of the state's exercise of the territorial authority, neither the jurisdiction over the territory can be exercised.

In the specialized legal doctrine, territorial supremacy is the mandate of the state in the exercise of full and exclusive power within the boundaries of the state territory. Territorial supremacy is provided and guaranteed both by the state's internal legislation and by the norms of international law [2, p.76]. The fullness of the territorial sovereignty of a State is expressed in the fact that each State on its own territory is able to determine the extent and nature of its competences, to regulate social relations in the most varied fields, to impose its authority on the entire social mechanism and to manage resources and national wealth [3, p.27].

In the relations of international law, the territory of the state is an element of particular importance, as it is a fundamental value for the existence of the states itself. Alongside the population, the territory is one of the material factors of the existence of the state [3, p.22]. On its territory, the state exercises its sovereignty fully and exclusively and acts in order to carry out its responsibilities and functions, and the other states are obliged not to damage territorial integrity [4, p.112].

An important element of territorial domination is the application of extraterritorial jurisdiction, accor-

ding to which the jurisdiction of the state over its citizens extends to international field [5, p.99]. On the basis of this principle, the state laws affect its citizens and stateless persons who live permanently in that state while they are abroad [6, p.112]. This applies even to law enforcement coercive branches, such as criminal law and contravention law.

Another principle of extraterritorial jurisdiction, quite widespread, is the principle of defense. On its basis, the state has the right to prosecute persons who are not its citizens for committing crimes outside the territory but against the interests of the state or its citizens [7, p.23]. Extraterritorial criminal jurisdiction can also be exercised on the basis of the principle of universality, according to which any state is entitled to institute criminal proceedings against a person who committed outside the state territory an offense under international law [8, p.211]. However, the fullness and exclusivity of territorial sovereignty does not exclude that a state, by its own will and under conditions established by international agreements, allows other states and their citizens' access to their own territory and some rights in its use, generally on the basis of reciprocity [9, p.93]. Thus, states grant each other the right to use the land, air, sea and river means of transportation on their territories, the right to trade and do business, the right to use their facilities or funds within certain limits, etc. Also, in the framework of international cooperation, states can commit themselves to abstain on their own territory from certain activities, such as the placement of categories of weapons, troop movements or military applications [6, p.125], or the construction of facilities that would harm to the environment and cause damage to other states, to introduce restrictions on the conduct of activities or to submit within their right to legislate conditions and limits established by the international conventions in which they take a part [10, p.22].

The case of the military from the contingent of the Russian armed forces in the conflict zone of the Republic of Moldova

This brief analysis of how states exercise jurisdiction allows us to find that competition of jurisdictions may arise in some situations. There is also the military case in the contingent of the Russian Federation's armed forces, located in the conflict zone in Transnistria, involved in the incident that took place on January 1, 2012 on the bridge from Vadul lui Voda (Republic of Moldova), which led to the death of a young Moldovan man.

The Russian soldier shot the young man at the checkpoint in a security area that was under the control and command of the Russian soldiers. The control point was located in the security zone established by the Agreement from 1999 on the end of the military conflict in the Transnistrian region and was under the control of the Russian military.

This case (*Pisari v. the Republic of Moldova and Russia*) was examined by the European Court, which established that neither the Russian Federation nor the Republic of Moldova had disputed their jurisdiction in this case. When a state's soldiers are sent to the territory of another state, the extra-territorial force they use may extend the jurisdiction of the state over the actions of its militaries [11].

In this context, the Russian Federation has the right to apply its personal jurisdiction to the military, since they possess Russian citizenship and the Republic of Moldova has the right to apply the territorial jurisdiction, as the incident took place on the territory of the Republic of Moldova. Only the Republic of Moldova can apply its jurisdiction if it has access to this person, whether it is detained by the Moldovan authorities or is extradited upon the request of the Republic of Moldova from the territory of a state with which we have such a signed agreement. As for the Russian Federation, it is evident that it will not extradite them, since one of the principles of consti-

titutional law provides for the non-admission of extradition of its own citizens. This principle is universal and does not require a detailed description. On the other hand, the parents of the young man considered that the Moldovan authorities were not responsible for the death of their son and had done everything they could reasonably investigate his death. Therefore, they no longer wanted to prosecute their claim against the Republic of Moldova. Finally, the Court accepted this claim of the applicants and decided to remove from its role the head of claim against the Republic of Moldova.

Practice shows that the members of the armed forces most often commit crimes, including serious ones. Given the fact that the Republic of Moldova de facto does not exercise jurisdiction over the members of the military contingent of the Russian Federation, it is equally in relation to persons committing crimes on the territory of the left bank of the Dniester, a territory which is outside the jurisdiction of Chisinau, so the logical question arises what will be the solution.

Expressing this opinion, the author believes there may be the following solutions. Regarding the persons who commit crimes on the territory of the left bank of the Dniester river, the solution would be to open a criminal investigation and to begin the international search, thus limiting their traffic space. In addition, we emphasize that for certain categories of offenses committed on the territory of the Republic of Moldova, such as war crimes, crimes against humanity, genocide, and acts of torture, the prescription term cannot be applied.

Regarding the exercise of jurisdiction over members of the military contingent of the Russian Federation, we find that the legal solution in the given case is appeal of the Republic of Moldova's authorities to the competent structures of the Russian Federation regarding the establishment of a working group and the examination of the case by presenting the respec-

tive evidence. Under the circumstances in which the offense was committed under the laws of both states (double criminality), the person concerned had to be put to justice by the Russian authorities. Otherwise, the same solution remained - starting the criminal investigation and international search of the person concerned. This is the ideal solution, but regretfully, in practice, things have been different.

In the specialized doctrine, the opinion was expressed that the impossibility of applying the jurisdiction of the state on its own territory to foreign soldiers is not conditioned by the legality of the stationing of the foreign armed forces [12, p. 121]. In the case of an armed occupation, international law is applied in practice, it is obvious that the respective state jurisdiction applies to the respective military [13, p.56]. Under the conditions of the stationing of foreign armed forces under an agreement, as a rule, the conventional provisions establish firmly that members of the respective armed forces fall under the jurisdiction of their own state. Under the conditions of the stationing of foreign armed forces under an agreement, as a rule, the conventional provisions establish firmly that members of the respective armed forces fall under the jurisdiction of their own state. It is interesting that in the case of the Republic of Moldova we can not talk about the applicability of a regime of occupation in the classical sense, since the stationing of the Russian forces at the beginning represented the effects of the ex-Soviet collapse, and no legal document was subsequently signed (which would produce international legal effects) between the Republic of Moldova and the Russian Federation, which would provide for the withdrawal of the Russian Federation's armed forces from the territory of the Republic of Moldova, including the terms of this withdrawal.

Foreign armed forces that are on the territory of the state, despite the absence of its approval, according to the traditional doctrine of international

law, enjoy immunity and externality [14, p.91]. In the case of military occupation, these forces are not subject to the jurisdiction of the occupied state, they are under the jurisdiction of the occupying state, which has to apply the provisions of the Hague regulations, respecting the laws and customs of war on land [15].

In other cases, the military of the hostile armed forces abroad is, in principle, immune from the offenses committed officially. However, the scope of this immunity is very limited, as most crimes committed by foreign soldiers are considered war crimes against which immunity is absent [12, p. 87].

The murder of the civilian population of the counterpart, the destruction and plundering of their assets are considered as crimes, provided for by the Fourth Geneva Convention [16]. Immunity for such crimes exists only in cases where the foreign military steals the property belonging to another foreign military. Obviously, such a special status cannot affect international law and state immunity *ratione materiae* in relation to war crimes, crimes against humanity and genocide. It appears that the special status of the foreign armed forces has nothing to do with the criminal prosecution exercised by the International Criminal Court.

The obligation to prosecute persons who have committed crimes or have subjected someone to torture cannot be denied based on a bilateral agreement between the states parties at the Conventions against torture [17] or on the Geneva Conventions. At the same time, some deviations from both parties are admitted taking into account the obligations provided in the Customs Agreements. That is why the agreements on the status of the armed forces, which establish immunities beforehand in relation to torture and war crimes, violate the obligations of the participants in such agreements, according to the conventions mentioned. The ones outlined are also applicable to the Convention on Genocide [18].

We should recognize that not only the Republic of Moldova faces such a problem. State practice shows us that in most cases (that means that this rule applies not just to states with authoritarian regimes, but also to states with a high level of democracy, such as USA, Great Britain, France, Canada, etc.) persons that have committed serious violations in armed conflicts or peacekeeping operations are formally punished. In some cases, the *jus cogens*, which represent the “core” of international humanitarian law, are ignored. The problem lies in the fact that such situations are often solved on the basis of political considerations, and therefore the level of applicability of the rule of law largely depends on the political factor.

Aspects regarding the application of the norms of international humanitarian law in the settlement of the Transnistrian conflict

The concept of international humanitarian law has a lot of substitutes, initially entering the language of law under the name of “Law of War” (“Droit de la guerre”, “Kriegsrecht”), with two meanings: *jus ad bellum*, that designates the rules on the conditions under which a State may use the armed force and *jus in bello*, the set of rules applicable between the parties of the armed conflict [19].

With the creation of the International Committee of the Red Cross in 1863, which undertook the task of stimulating the codification of the rules of the protection of combatants and non-combatants, as well as of civilians, *jus in bello* divides into two branches - the Law of War and Humanitarian Law [20]. Coding conferences at the end of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries enshrined the law of war in the formula “laws and customs of war”. Subsequently, the last major codification of 1977 brought together the two branches - the Law of War and Humanitarian Law - into a new concept: “The International Humanitarian Law of Armed Conflicts,” which is the official name.

Taking into account that international humanitarian law applies only in times of armed conflict, we should clarify whether there is an armed conflict in the Transnistrian region. In that case, we rely on the Court of Appeal’s definition of the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY) on the Tadić case, which states that “an armed conflict exists whenever there is a use of armed force between states or durable violence between authorities and organized armed groups or between such groups within a state” [21].

Although, the Transnistrian conflict could be considered frozen since the hostilities ceased in 1992, the Tadic decision seems to include the conflict between the Republic of Moldova and Transnistria as an “armed conflict” because there was a prolonged armed conflict between governmental authority (Republic of Moldova) and an organized armed group (Transnistria), but a peaceful settlement has not been achieved yet.

Would this suggest that international humanitarian law should be applied in the Transnistrian region, as Tadić defines international humanitarian law also extends in peacetime? Besides the cessation of hostilities, will it be until the end of the peace or until a peaceful solution is achieved?

Although a number of initiatives bringing the peace to Transnistria were adopted, they have failed, and Russian troops are still present in the region in a capacity of peacekeepers. Transnistria came forward with an initiative to strengthen the statehood, whereas having no recognition from the international community and a little chance to obtain such recognition. In the case of the withdrawal of Russian peacekeeping troops, a military conflict can appear again. Therefore, we conclude that a situation of armed conflict has existed and continues to exist in the transnistrian region and that international humanitarian law should apply.

There is necessary to determine the categorization of this conflict. If the involvement of the Russian Federation has any impact on this categorization, there is a need to understand the potential extent of the application of international humanitarian law in the region. Underscore that that the USSR was a party of the Geneva Conventions of 1949 [22], including the Additional Protocols I and II of 1977 [23] and the Republic of Moldova was a party by succession, in accordance with the provisions of the Government Decision of R.M. no.442 of 17.07.2015 for the approval of the Regulation on the mechanism for the conclusion, application, and termination of international treaties [24].

In recent years, there have been a number of calls for the modification of international humanitarian law by abandoning the division of international and non-international armed conflicts, but the respective classification is still in force [25, p.34]. Within this context, the question is whether the involvement of the Russian Federation has transformed the transnistrian conflict into an international armed conflict, thus triggering the potential for the application of the entire corpus of international humanitarian law. Moreover, it is important that a legal regime, and especially an expansive legal regime, is effectively applied in cases such as Transnistria, because, as this territory is a de facto state, there are no obligations and possibilities to apply the standards and international norms, leaving the population of Transnistria without international legal protection [26, p.63].

The regime of international humanitarian law offers a certain level of protection for the population, prosecuting alleged offenders for war crimes, such as rape, murder and torture, protecting civilian assets [27, p.118]. However, as mentioned above, the potential level of protection depends on the classification of the conflict.

Although, it is often claimed that the situation in Transnistria is used as an instrument of the Russian Federation's policy of "close vicinity" [28, p.18],

there is a need of a detailed examination of the conflict to determine the extent of Russian Federation's involvement in the planning and managing of the Transnistrian governance. This issue, as well as the continued existence of the de facto state of Transnistria, was addressed by the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR) in the case of Ilascu and others vs. Moldova and the Russian Federation [29]. The court examined the issue in order to determine whether Russia's involvement in the conflict was sufficient to bring the conflict under Russia's jurisdiction. This case examined by the ECHR is the main source of information regarding the involvement of the Russian Federation in the transnistrian conflict.

The court considered in its judgment that: "The Russian Federation is responsible for the illegal acts committed by the transnistrian separatists, taking into account the political and military support granted to help in the establishment of the separatist regime and in the participation of russian members of the armed forces in the fighting. Thus, the russian authorities contributed both militarily and politically to the creation of the separatist regime in the transnistrian region, which is part of the territory of the Republic of Moldova". The court also noted that, even after the ceasefire agreement in July 1992, the Russian Federation continued to support the transnistrian separatist regime militarily, politically and economically, "thus allowing them to survive, strengthen and obtain a certain amount of autonomy vis-à-vis Moldova". In this way, the ECHR established a strong link between the Russian Federation and the Tiraspol authorities, talking about a «decisive influence» and even about an «effective authority».

Specifics of international law's application in the context of the territorial conflict in Abkhazia and South Ossetia

In the specialized literature, most authors considered that the disputed territories of Eastern Europe

are the direct product of the former Soviet Union policy for the gradual change of state borders in order to thwart any possible separatist attempts and to ensure the unity of the USSR [30, p.65].

According to the Law of the USSR of April 3, 1990 “On the procedure for solving the problems regarding the exit of the Union Republics from the composition of the USSR” [31], the peoples of the autonomous republics and the autonomous entities had the right to decide independently whether to remain in the USSR, raising the issue of their legal status. Separate state entities within the USSR could only be considered new states if the interests of all the peoples of the USSR were taken into account and after the procedure that ensured each nation the right to choose state membership.

Without complying with the provisions of the USSR Law of April 3, 1990 the collapse of the Soviet Union led to the complex conflicts in the former Soviet republics, which have not yet been resolved and continue to provoke tensions between the Russian Federation and its neighbors. The examples are the conflicts in South Ossetia and Abkhazia that have degenerated into violent conflicts, ethnic cleansing and severe tensions between the Russian Federation and Georgia.

The self-proclamation of independence by South Ossetia and Abkhazia has sparked scientific debates on the applicability of the right to self-determination, including the right to secession [32, p.64]. Self-determination and secession are fundamental issues of public international law. In this case, some researchers (C.Walter, A.Ungern-Sternberg, etc.) mentioned that the right to self-determination and even to secession enjoyed by peoples and ethnic groups is in direct conflict with the sovereignty and territorial integrity of the states [33, p.293]. Other researchers have stated that the right of states to territorial integrity may not be absolute and unqualified, because “the development of international human rights law

has limited the concept of state sovereignty in many respects”[34, p.21]. This approach introduces the idea of corrective secession. That is a set of conditions that could justify the secession of a people or ethnic group in its own state as a last resort measure “[35, p.67].

The doctrine of secession a “last resort” has been used by many states that have recognized Kosovo. Similarly, the Russian Federation has taken the secession doctrine as a remedy to justify the recognition of the independence of South Ossetia and Abkhazia after the armed conflict with Georgia in 2008 [35, p.68]. Thus, South Ossetia and Abkhazia *de jure* remain part of Georgia, although Georgia does not have effective control over these self-proclaimed republics. A similar situation exists in the Republic of Moldova, in relation to the self-proclaimed republic of Transnistria.

From the perspective of political science, these conflicts are labeled as “frozen conflicts” which means that although the military hostilities have ceased, solutions for resolving these conflicts have not been found [33, p.295]. From the point of view of international law, “frozen conflicts” indicate competitive sovereignty over a certain territory and a possible collision of the different norms of international law, in which a group invokes the right to self-determination, while the mother state demands the respect of the territorial integrity of the states [36, p.35]. Therefore, as in the case of Transnistria, South Ossetia and Abkhazia claim that they have not only the right to self-determination, but also the right to secession, through territorial separation from Georgia. Both South Ossetia and Abkhazia base their claims on allegations of discrimination and massive human rights violations committed by Georgia, grounds that constitute the basis of the right to secession as a “last resort remedy” [33, p.296].

South Ossetia declared independence from the Soviet Socialist Republic of Georgia in 1991. The

Georgian government responded by abolishing the autonomy of South Ossetia and trying to regain control of the region by force. The escalation of the crisis led to the war in Ossetia in the period from 1991 to 1992 and to the battles of 2004 and 2008 respectively.

On November 10, 1989, the XII Session of the Council of People's Deputies from the South Ossetian Autonomous Region decided to transform this region into the Autonomous Republic of the Soviet Socialist Republic of Georgia. In response, the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Socialist Soviet Republic of Georgia declared this decision unconstitutional [37, p.75].

One year later, on September 20, 1990, the Council of Deputies of South Ossetia adopted the Declaration of State Sovereignty, there was decided to form the Soviet Democratic Republic of South Ossetia in the composition of the USSR, and on November 28, 1990 the state entity was renamed in the Soviet Republic of South Ossetia. Accordingly, on December 11, 1990, the Supreme Council of the Republic of Georgia, chaired by Z.Gam-Sakhurdia, adopted the Law on the abolition of the South Ossetian Autonomous Region [38, p.25-26].

From this point of view, in the legal doctrine of the Russian Federation, critical opinions were expressed [39, p.141], and namely, the adoption of the Law on the abolition of the South Ossetia Autonomous Region was contradicted to the provisions of Art.3 of the USSR Law of April 26, 1990 regarding the delimitation of powers between the USSR and the subjects of the federation, which established that "the territory of a union, autonomous republics or an autonomous entity cannot be changed without their agreement [40], and paragraph (2) of Article 6 of this law attributed it the exclusive jurisdiction of the Soviet Union the admission in the USSR of the new Union republics, the approval of the formation of new autonomous republics and the approval of the changes in the statute

of the existing autonomous republics, in the statute of the autonomous regions and autonomous districts.

After the collapse of the USSR (1991), the Supreme Council of South Ossetia appointed a referendum on the independence and accession of the region to the Russian Federation. During the referendum of January 19, 1992, the majority of the participants voted for independence and accession to Russia. Thus, on May 29, 1992, the Supreme Council of the Republic of South Ossetia proclaimed the independence and creation of an independent state - South Ossetia [39, p.142]. In their turn, the Russian Federation immediately recognized the independence of South Ossetia, openly and publicly declaring its decision to support the de facto authorities of these territories politically, financially and militarily [41, p.299].

During the period of 1992 to 1996, South Ossetia formed its own state structures, in particular, the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the military departments. Although not recognized internationally, the republic had a Constitution and Parliament, and the presidential institution was formed in 1996. The first presidential election in South Ossetia was held on November 10, 1996 [42, p.168].

Contrary to all the peaceful settlement agreements of the Georgian-Ossetian conflict, on the night of August 8, 2008, there took place military conflicts between the Georgian and South Ossetian forces. Russian peacekeeping forces were also involved in the military conflict.

As a result of the negotiations between Georgia, the Russian Federation and the institutions of the European Union, six principles for the settlement of the conflict between Georgia and South Ossetia were approved: 1) non-use of military force; 2) final cessation of hostilities; 3) free access to humanitarian aid; 4) withdrawal of Georgia's armed forces from the conflict perimeter; 5) maintaining the peacekeeping armed forces of the Russian Federation on the outbreak of hostilities until the creation of international

mechanisms; 6) initiating international discussions on the future status of South Ossetia and Abkhazia, as well as on the ways to ensure sustainable security in these regions.

On August 26, 2008, the President of the Russian Federation signed Decree No. 1261 “On the recognition of the Republic of South Ossetia”. The Decree indicated that the recognition is based on the will of the people of South Ossetia. At the same time, the task of the Russian Ministry of Foreign Affairs was to arrange negotiations with the South Ossetia administration in order to establish diplomatic relations of cooperation and mutual assistance.

Although the rules of international law protect the territorial integrity of Georgia, there were states that did not take into account the international legal framework. Thus, on September 5, 2008, the Republic of Nicaragua recognized the independence of South Ossetia and became the first country in Latin America to manifest such a gesture. Later, on September 10, 2009, Venezuelan President Hugo Chavez announced that Venezuela recognizes the independence of South Ossetia and Abkhazia. In the same context, the leaders of states such as Armenia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan condemned Georgia’s actions in South Ossetia and supported the actions of the Russian Federation at the summit of the Collective Security Treaty Organization in Moscow. On the other hand, on September 1, 2008, the European Union condemned the unilateral recognition of Abkhazia and South Ossetia by the Russian Federation, stating that this decision was unacceptable and urged all states not to recognize the independence of the self-proclaimed republics.

From the perspective of the scientific research we carry out, the military actions between the Georgian forces and those of South Ossetia need to be evaluated from the point of view of international law. Thus, Russian researchers concluded that Georgia’s actions were illegal. As an argument, it was invo-

ked that Georgia concluded an international agreement with the participation of South Ossetia and the Russian Federation in 1992 and 1994, according to which the parties committed to solve all the disputed issues exclusively through peaceful means, without using force or threatening to use it. Georgia, violating the agreement and international legal principles regarding the non-use of force and the threat of force, committed an act of aggression against South Ossetia [43, p.45].

Most Russian authors hold by the opinion that Georgia attacked South Ossetia and the Russian peacekeeping forces on August 8, 2008. It was mentioned that the Russian Federation was obliged to use its inherent right to self-defense, enshrined in Art. 51 of the UN Charter. The Russian side’s use of force was intended to protect the Russian peacekeeping contingent from Georgia’s illegal actions, which was performing its functions in South Ossetia in accordance with the provisions of an international mandate. Therefore, the Russian researchers considered that Georgia’s intervention was an act of aggression, and the Russian Federation was entitled to self-defense. As regards South Ossetia, it has ensured its security based on the right to self-determination through the separation and formation of an independent state [44, p.54]. Georgia appealed to the principle of territorial integrity, while South Ossetia appealed to peoples’ right to self-determination. As a result of the armed attack on South Ossetia, Georgia violated the principles of international law, namely: prohibition of the use of force or threat of force, respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms, self-determination of the people.

Referințe:

1. Luban D., O’Sullivan J., Stewart D. International and Transnational Criminal Law, 3rd Edition. - London: Wolters Kluwer, 2018.

2. Koskeniemi M., Rech W., Fonseca M.J. International law and empire: historical explorations. - Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017.
3. Wojtyczek K. Territory and the Principle of Territoriality in Public International Law. // European Review of Public Law (Greece), 2017, Vol.29, No.1 (103).
4. Ryngaert C. Jurisdiction in International Law. Second Edition. - Oxford: University Press, 2015, p.112.
5. Shelton D. International law and domestic legal systems: incorporation, transformation and persuasion. - Oxford: University Press, 2011, p.99.
6. Björkvinsson D. The intersection of international law and domestic law: a theoretical and practical analysis. - Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Pub. Ltd, 2015, p.112.
7. Kjeldgaard-Pedersen A. The International Legal Personality of the Individual. - Oxford: University Press, 2018, p.23.
8. Luban D., O'Sullivan J., Stewart D. International and Transnational Criminal Law, 3rd Edition. - London: Wolters Kluwer, 2018.
9. Canefe N. International Criminal Law and Limits of Universal Jurisdiction in the Global South: A Critical Discussion on Crimes Against Humanity. PhD Dissertations. - Toronto, 2018.
10. Guyomar M. Territorial Belonging – Inclusion and Exclusion from State Territories. // European Review of Public Law (Greece), 2017, Vol.29, No.1 (103), p.22.
11. Extra-territorial jurisdiction of States Parties to the European Convention on Human Rights, Pisari v. the Republic of Moldova and Russia, https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/FS_Extra-territorial_jurisdiction_ENG.pdf (accessed on 12.05.2019).
12. Shaw-Malcolm N. The International Law of Territory. - Oxford: University Press, 2018.
13. Schuett R., Stirk P. The Concept of the State in International Relations Philosophy, Sovereignty and Cosmopolitanism. - Edinburgh: University Press, 2015, p.56.
14. Ryngaert C. Jurisdiction in International Law. Second Edition. - Oxford: University Press, 2015, p.91.
15. Convention (IV) respecting the Laws and Customs of War on Land and its annex: Regulations concerning the Laws and Customs of War on Land. The Hague, 18 October 1907, <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/applic/ihl/ihl.nsf/Treaty.xsp?action=openDocument&documentId=4D47F92DF3966A7EC12563CD002D6788> (accessed at 18.05.2019).
16. Convention (IV) relative to the Protection of Civilian Persons in Time of War, Geneva, 12 August 1949, https://www.un.org/en/genocideprevention/documents/atrocities-crimes/Doc.33_GC-IV-EN.pdf (accessed at 18.05.2019).
17. Convenția nr.1984 din 10.12.1984 împotriva torturii și altor pedepse ori tratamente cu cruzime, inumane sau degradante. // Tratatate Internaționale la care Republica Moldova este parte. – Chisinau, 1995, nr.1.
18. Convenția nr.1948 din 09.12.1948 pentru prevenirea și reprimarea crimei de genocid, adoptată de Adunarea generală a Națiunilor Unite prin Rezoluția 260A (III) din 09.12.1948. // Tratatate Internaționale la care Republica Moldova este parte. – Chisinau, 1998, nr.1.
19. Liebllich E. On the Continuous and Concurrent Application of *ad Bellum* and *in Bello* Proportionality. // Case Western Reserve Journal of International Law (USD), 2016, Vol.48, Issue 1-2.
20. Liebllich E. The Facilitative Function of Jus in Bello. // European Journal of International Law (USD), 2019, Vol. 30, Issue 1.
21. Prosecutor vs Tadić, Appeal Chamber Decision, (Case No. IT-94-1-A), 14 December 1995, Tadić Jurisdiction Decision. // <http://www.unhcr.org/refworld/docid/40277f504.html> (accessed on 15.05.2019).
22. The Convention I for the amelioration of the condition of the wounded and sick in armed forces in the field signed on 12 August 1949 in Geneva. In: International Treaties (Humanitarian Law). Official edition. Chisinau: Garuda-art, 1999; The Convention II for the improvement of the fate of wounded, sick and shipwrecked military personnel at sea during war signed on 12 August 1949 in Geneva. In: International Treaties (Humanitarian Law). Official edition. Chisinau: Garuda-art, 1999; The Convention III on the treatment of prisoners of war signed on 12 August 1949 in Geneva. In: International Treaties (Humanitarian Law). Official edition. Chisinau: Garuda-art, 1999; The Convention IV on the protection of civilians during wartime signed on 12 August 1949 in Geneva. In: International Treaties (Humanitarian Law). Official edition. - Chisinau: Garuda-art, 1999.

23. Additional Protocol I to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 on the Protection of Victims of International Armed Conflict signed July 10, 1977. In: *International Treaties (Humanitarian Law)*. Official edition. Chisinau: Garuda-art, 1999; Additional Protocol II to the Geneva Conventions of 1949 on the Protection of Victims of Armed Conflict not having an international character signed on July 10, 1977. In: *International Treaties (Humanitarian Law)*. Official edition. - Chisinau: Garuda-art, 1999.
24. RM's Government Decision no.442 of 17.07.2015 for the approval of the Regulation on the mechanism for the conclusion, application and termination of international treaties. // *Monitorul Oficial of the Republic of Moldova*, 2015, no.190-196.
25. Willmott D. Removing the distinction between international and non-international armed conflict in the Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court. In: *Melbourne Journal of International Law (Australia)*, 2004, nr.5.
26. O'Reilly K., Higgins N. The Role of the Russian Federation in the Pridnestrovian Conflict: an International Humanitarian Law Perspective. In: *Irish Studies in International Affairs (Ireland)*, 2008, vol.19.
27. Sassòli M. *International humanitarian law: rules, controversies, and solutions to problems arising in warfare*. - Northampton: Edward Elgar Pub., 2019.
28. Voronovici A. Internationalist Separatism and the Political Use of „Historical Statehood” in the Unrecognized Republics of Transnistria and Donbass. // *Problems of Post-Communism (USA)*, May 2019.
29. Case *Ilaşcu and others vs Moldova and Russia*, App. No.48787/99 (E.C.H.R., July 8, 2004), par.59. // [http://justice.md/file/CEDO_judgments/Moldova/ILASCU%20SI%20ALTII%20\(ro\).pdf](http://justice.md/file/CEDO_judgments/Moldova/ILASCU%20SI%20ALTII%20(ro).pdf) (accessed at 07.05.2019).
30. Riegl M., Doboš B. *Unrecognized states and secession in the 21st century*. - Cham: Springer, 2017.
31. Закон СССР от 3 апреля 1990 года №1409-1 „О порядке решения вопросов, связанных с выходом союзной республики из СССР”. // *Ведомости Съезда народных депутатов СССР и Верховного Совета СССР*, 1990, №15.
32. Шепенко Р.А. Реализация принципа самоопределения народов и налоговое право: опыт Грузии. // *Российский журнал правовых исследований*. 2017, № 2 (11).
33. Walter C., Ungern-Sternberg A. *Self-determination and secession in international law*. - Oxford: University Press, 2014.
34. Volk Ch. The Problem of Sovereignty in Globalized Times. // *Law, Culture and the Humanities (USA)*, 2019, no.2.
35. Laurinavičiūtė L., Biekša L. The Relevance of Remedial Secession in the Post-Soviet „Frozen Conflicts”. // *International Comparative Jurisprudence (Lithuania)*, 2015, Volume 1, Issue 1, p.67.
36. Distefano G. *Fundamentals of Public International Law. A Sketch of the International Legal Order*. - Brill: Nijhoff, 2019.
37. Saparov A. *From Conflict to Autonomy in the Caucasus: The Soviet Union and the Making of Abkhazia, South Ossetia and Nagorno Karabakh*. - London: Routledge, 2015.
38. Конфликты в Абхазии и Южной Осетии: документы 1989-2006 гг./сост. и коммент. М.А.Волхонский, В.А.Захаров, Н.Ю.Силаев. - Москва, 2008.
39. Khasanov A.A. International legal aspects of recognition of South Ossetia. // *Review of comparative analysis of foreign legislation and jurisprudence (Russian Federation)*, 2018, no.1.
40. Закон СССР от 26 апреля 1990 г. №1457-1 „О разграничении полномочий между Союзом ССР и субъектами Федерации”. // *Ведомости Съезда Народных Депутатов и Верховного Совета СССР*, 1990, №19.
41. Gerrits A., Bader M. Russian patronage over Abkhazia and South Ossetia: implications for conflict resolution. // *East European Politics (The Netherlands)*, 2016, Vol.32, Issue 3.
42. Cuestas-Zamora E.J. Fragmentación de la República de Georgia: perspectivas jurídicas de la separación de Abjasia y Osetia del Sur en Derecho Internacional Público. // *Revista Colombiana de Derecho Internacional*, 2015, no.26.
43. Плиев С.М. Признание Россией независимости Южной Осетии Абхазии: проблемы оценки и интеграции. // *Политические институты и процессы в эпоху глобализации: Сборник статей студентов, аспирантов и молодых ученых-политологов.* / Под ред. проф. Д.Е.Слизовского. - Москва: МАКС Пресс, 2011.

28.08.2019